

EXPLORING TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION KNOWLEDGE WITHIN COVID-19 CRISIS SET-UP: NARRATIVES OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract.The current study aimed to explore the lived experiences of the teachers as regard to their technology integration in new normal learning set-up and how they cope up with challenges. In this study, the researcher selected the 12 public elementary school teachers in Laak South District, Davao de Oro as the participants of the study. Purposive sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the participants. Qualitative research design using phenomenological method was employed. The data collected were thematics analysis. Findings revealed that on the lived experiences of the teachers as regard to the technology integration knowledge within COVID-19 crisis set-up, the emerging theme was Adaptation to Online Teaching with subthemes namely: technological proficiency and skills development; pedagogical innovations and experimentation; and lesson planning and curriculum adaptation. In addition, the theme that emerged on the participants' coping mechanism with regards to the challenges in relation to technology integration knowledge within COVID-19 crisis was Professional Development for Remote Learning with subthemes namely: online workshops and training; individualized professional development plans; and peer learning communities. Lastly, the emerging themes on the skills developed among public elementary school teachers were digital literacy enhancement; curriculum integration; and tech tools exploration. The study, therefore, conducted for further utilization of findings through publication in reputable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational management
2. technology integration
3. COVID-19 crisis set-up

1. Introduction

Exploring the technology integration knowledge of elementary school teachers during the pandemic using a phenomenological qualitative research design can offer valuable insights into the lived experiences, perceptions, and practices of educators in navigating the challenges and opportunities presented by remote and hybrid learning environments. Through phenomeno-

logical inquiry, researchers can identify the challenges and barriers that elementary school teachers encounter in integrating technology into their instruction during the pandemic. This may include issues related to access to technology resources, digital literacy skills, pedagogical support, and infrastructure limitations. Thus, a phenomenological qualitative research design

offers a rich and nuanced understanding of elementary school teachers' experiences with technology integration during the pandemic, providing insights that can inform policy, practice, and future research in the field of education. Many remote areas lack adequate internet connectivity, digital devices, and technological infrastructure, making it challenging for teachers to access online resources, communicate with students, and deliver remote instruction effectively. The lack of adequate internet connectivity, digital devices, and technological infrastructure in remote areas presents formidable obstacles for teachers seeking to integrate technology into their teaching during the pandemic (Voithofer Nelson, 2021). In Asia, teachers in remote areas have varying levels of digital literacy and technological proficiency, leading to disparities in their ability to navigate digital tools, platforms, and educational resources. Addressing these skills gaps requires targeted professional development and support initiatives (Kao et al., 2020). Taking things in Philippine setting, shifting from traditional classroom instruction to remote teaching requires teachers to adapt their pedagogical approaches, lesson plans, and instructional strategies. Teachers in remote areas require training and support to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices and facilitate engaging and interactive remote learning experiences (Mercado, Panganiban Ramos, 2019). More so, the availability of digital devices such as laptops, tablets, or smartphones is crucial for both teachers and students to engage in remote learning activities. However, in many remote areas, schools and households may lack sufficient access to these devices. Teachers may not have personal or school-provided devices to facilitate remote instruction, limiting their ability to create and deliver digital lessons, access online materials, or communicate with students (Santos Castro, 2021). In Laak South District, Davao de Oro, most schools the teachers knowledge in technology and the emphasis of the application for student technical difficulties for technology integration in all subject areas have become the major problem; source of frustration for teachers especially in the teaching and learning process. The low opportunity to integrate technology in the teaching process decreases students' interest to engage in class discussion, thus, resulting to poor academic achievement among students in the elementary level. The technical difficulties such as unstable source of electricity, low connectivity, virus attack, printer malfunctioning, and lack of technical assistance also resulted to teachers' discouragement from using computer technology during class discussion. This problem is similar to the difficulties faced by other schools in rural areas where technical problems become the major barrier for teachers. Cognizant of this dilemma, schools in Laak South District in Davao Oro have recognized the importance of technical support to assist teachers to integrate ICT in the classroom. Addressing these issues requires a multi-faceted approach that includes investment in technology infrastructure, targeted professional development for teachers, equitable access to digital resources, and support for teacher well-being and resilience. By addressing these challenges, education stakeholders can better support teachers in remote areas and ensure that all students have access to high-quality remote learning opportunities during the pandemic crisis and beyond. It is on this context that the researcher felt the need to fill-in the research gap of conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in Laak South District, Davao de Oro using a qualitative approach. Specifically, the researcher made use of phenomenological approach to have a better understanding of the technology integration knowledge of the teachers in post COVID-19 crisis which is found to be scarce. The present study intended to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding teacher's technology integration knowledge in Davao de Oro.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to explore the lived experiences of the teachers in public elementary schools in Laak South District, Davao de Oro as regards to their technology integration knowledge within COVID-19 crisis using qualitative approach, specifically, the phenomenological design wherein a semi-structured interview guide was administered through in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD). In-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD) were employed to generate insights, feedback on attitudes, and lived experiences of participants relevant to their technology integration knowledge of teachers within COVID-19 crisis in public elementary schools in Laak South District, Davao de Oro.

- (1) What are the experiences of the elementary teachers in public elementary schools as regard to their technology integration knowledge within COVID-19 crisis set-up?
- (2) How do participants cope up with the challenges in relation to technology integration within COVID-19 crisis set-up?
- (3) What are the skills developed by participants while integrating technology in their lesson within COVID-19 crisis set-up?

1.2. Theoretical Lens—A pragmatic paradigm was applied in this study. The pragmatic paradigm prioritized the practical application of research findings to address real-world problems. In the context of exploring the lived experiences of teachers on integrating technology during the pandemic crisis, a pragmatic approach would focus on understanding how teachers' experiences with technology integration translate into actionable strategies and practices that can improve teaching and learning outcomes. As noted by Kaushik and Walsh (2019), citing the pragmatic paradigm emphasized the study's relevance and utility in addressing practical concerns. Also, pragmatism acknowledged the importance of understanding the specific context in which research occurred. In the context of exploring the lived experiences of teachers on integrating technology during the pandemic crisis, a pragmatic approach would focus on understanding how teachers' experiences with technology integration translate into actionable strategies and practices that can improve teaching and learning outcomes. Pragmatic research often involves a focus on action and intervention. In the context of technology integration, this may involve developing and implementing interventions or initiatives aimed at supporting teachers in enhancing their technology integration skills and practices (Kelly Cordeiro, 2020). One aspect of pragmatic research in technology integration is the development of targeted interventions designed to address specific needs or challenges faced by teachers. These interventions may include training programs, workshops, or professional development initiatives aimed at improving teachers' technological proficiency, pedagogical skills, and confidence in using technology effectively in their teaching practices. Moreover, this study is anchored on the TPACK Framework by Misha and Koehler (2006). The TPACK framework suggests that effective technology integration requires teachers to possess knowledge and skills in three key areas: technological knowledge (TK), pedagogical knowledge (PK), and content knowledge (CK). Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of understanding how these knowledge domains intersect and interact to support meaningful learning experiences. Moreover, TPACK framework emphasizes that effective technology integration occurs at the intersection of these three knowledge domains: TK, PK, and CK. Teachers must possess a balanced blend of technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge to leverage technology effectively in their teaching practices.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of Study

1.3. Analytical Framework—The framework of analysis referred to a structured approach used to analyze and interpret data collected during a case study. It involved several key steps, including data organization, coding, theme development, interpretation, and synthesis of findings. The framework of analysis was a critical component of the case study approach to studying the learning patterns and behavior of fatherless children. Proper implementation of the framework ensured rigor, validity, and transparency in data analysis, ultimately leading to valuable insights and contributions to the field of education and child development. Moreover, proper implementation of the framework enabled the researcher to interpret findings in a meaningful and insightful manner. By systematically analyzing data and identifying key themes and patterns, researchers could generate rich insights into the factors influencing the learning patterns and behavior of fatherless children. The researcher observed several steps in conducting thematic analysis. By following that step-by-step framework of analysis, researchers

could conduct a rigorous and insightful case study on the learning patterns and behavior of fatherless children, providing valuable contributions to the field of education and child development. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consisted of several phases used in analyzing the data. **Case Selection.** Identify and select a representative case or cases of fatherless children whose learning patterns and behavior will be studied. Consider factors such as diversity in demographics, geographical location, and educational context to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. **Data Collection.** Collect data using multiple methods, such as in-depth interviews, drawing from participants, and document review. Ensure that data collection methods are appropriate for capturing the complexity and nuances of the children’s learning experiences. **Data Organization.** Organize the collected data, including interview transcripts, drawings, and documents, into a structured dataset. Label and categorize the data according to key variables and themes relevant to the research questions.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design that was used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection, the data analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical consideration.

Fig. 2. Framework of Analysis

The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) is optimal for collecting data on individuals’ personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when sensitive topics are being explored. Focus groups are effective in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry which asks the questions, “What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people? “the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand challenges of the floating teachers. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that is greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg. In the preparation of this paper, the researcher employed artificial intelligence tools for proofreading. Specifically, AI was utilized to enhance the accuracy, coherence, and overall quality of the manuscript. This practice is being explicitly stated to maintain transparency and adhere to ethical standards in research. The usage of AI for proofreading reflects a commitment to leveraging advanced technologies responsibly and acknowledges the increasing prevalence and capability of AI in academic and professional writing.

2.1. *Philosophical Assumptions*—The subjective constructivism viewpoint was held as the ontological consideration in this study. According to Barbehön (2020), constructivism acknowledged that individuals interpreted their experiences in unique ways based on their personal backgrounds, beliefs, and social contexts. In the context of technology integration, researchers investigated how teachers interpreted the role of technology in teaching and learning, how they perceived its impact on student engagement and learning outcomes, and how

they conceptualized effective practices for integrating technology into instruction. Furthermore, constructivism emphasized the importance of active, student-centered learning experiences. In the context of technology integration, the researchers explored how teachers' pedagogical beliefs and practices had shifted during the pandemic to accommodate remote or hybrid learning environments. This involved investigating changes in instructional strategies, assessment methods, and approaches to student engagement facilitated by technology. Constructivism acknowledged that individuals interpreted their experiences in unique ways based on their personal backgrounds, beliefs, and social contexts (MacLeod, Burm Mann,

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Qualitative assumptions provide the philosophical foundation for qualitative research methodologies, guiding researchers in their exploration and understanding of social phenomena. These assumptions shape the researcher's perspective, approach, and methods, ultimately influencing the outcomes and interpretations of qualitative research studies (Levitt, 2021). According to Pearse (2021), qualitative research assumes an interpretive approach to inquiry, recognizing that researchers play an active role in constructing meaning from data. This assumption acknowledges that data are not objective or value-free but are influenced by the researcher's interpretations, biases, and perspectives. In the context of the current study, the researcher's key assumption was that participants' subjective experiences and interpretations held significance and provided valuable insights into the phenomenon being studied. In this case, the researcher likely assumed that teachers' experiences with technology integration during the pandemic were rich in meaning and could shed light on the challenges, successes, and changes in pedagogical practices brought about by remote or hybrid learning environments. Addi-

2022). From a constructivist perspective, the researchers sought to identify the affordances of technology in supporting student-centered, inquiry-based learning experiences. This might have involved examining how teachers leveraged digital tools, online resources, and multimedia platforms to facilitate collaborative learning, problem-solving, and knowledge construction among students. Additionally, the phenomenological study aimed to uncover the lived experiences and perspectives of teachers as they navigated technology integration during the pandemic. The researchers sought to understand how teachers made sense of their experiences, challenges, and successes in incorporating technology into their teaching practices.

tionally, the researcher likely operated under the assumption that participants' experiences were shaped by their personal and contextual factors. Phenomenology acknowledges that individuals interpret their experiences based on their unique backgrounds, beliefs, and social contexts. As such, the researcher likely sought to understand how these factors influenced teachers' approaches to technology integration and their perceptions of its impact on teaching and learning. Moreover, the researcher may have assumed that participants' accounts of their experiences would provide valuable insights into effective practices for technology integration in education. By exploring teachers' lived experiences, the researcher likely aimed to uncover strategies, challenges, and recommendations for enhancing technology integration in teaching practices, particularly in the context of remote or hybrid learning. Overall, the qualitative assumptions underlying the phenomenological study likely centered on valuing participants' subjective experiences, recognizing the diversity of experiences among teachers, acknowledging the influence of personal and contextual factors, and seeking insights into effective practices for technology integration in education.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study used a qualitative design following a phenomenological study method. Qualitative research design refers to the systematic plan or framework used to conduct qualitative research studies (Williams, 2019). According to Cypress (2019), it emphasizes understanding social phenomena through the subjective experiences, meanings, and interpretations of individuals or groups within their natural contexts. Qualitative research design is used to explore, describe, interpret, and understand social phenomena in depth, providing insights into complex human behavior, interactions, and experiences. It often involves qualitative data collection methods such as interviews, observations, focus groups, and document analysis, which are used to gather data that capture the depth and complexity of social phenomena. Phenomenological qualitative research design was an approach that sought to understand individuals' lived experiences and the meanings they assigned to those experiences. It explored the essence of phenomena as they were perceived by participants, aiming to uncover the underlying structures and processes that shaped their subjective realities (Williams, 2021). In this approach, researchers focused on gathering rich, detailed descriptions of participants' experiences through methods such as interviews, observations, and journaling. They often employed techniques such as bracketing, epoché, and phenomenological reduction to set aside preconceived notions and allow the participants' experiences to emerge without bias (Petitmengin, Remillieux Valenzuela-Moguillansky, 2019). The phenomenological qualitative research design was well-suited for studying technology integration knowledge of teachers during the pandemic in remote areas, offering a comprehensive understanding of teachers' experiences, perspectives, and practices in these contexts. By employing phenomenological methods, the researcher could delve deeply into these experiences to gain insights into the specific contexts, challenges, and successes encountered by teachers in remote settings. Additionally, phenomenological research allowed researchers to capture the subjective realities of teachers in these contexts, acknowledging the diversity of perspectives and experiences that may have existed. This approach could uncover nuanced insights that may not have been apparent through quantitative or standardized assessments.

2.4. *Research Participants*—The selected participants of this study were the twelve (12) elementary school teachers in public schools in Laak South District, Davao de Oro. In selecting the participants, the researcher made use of purposive sampling technique. According to Suryani and Herianti (2023), purposive sampling is a technique wherein a sample were chosen based on their particular features or characteristics which enable detailed exploration and understanding of the constructs under the study and research questions. As denoted by Campbell et al. (2020), purposive sampling offers flexibility and customization in participant selection, allowing researchers to focus on specific attributes or criteria that are most relevant to their research questions. While purposive sampling may lack the representativeness of probability sampling methods, it can be a valuable approach for generating in-depth insights and understanding complex phenomena within targeted populations. In selecting the participants, the researcher implemented certain inclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria are as follows: elementary school teachers currently teaching in Laak South District, Davao de Oro; teachers who have experience with integrating technology into their classroom instruction; teachers who have taught during the pandemic and have experience with remote or hybrid teach-

ing modalities; and teachers who are willing to participate in the study and provide detailed information about their experiences with technology integration. In contrary, teachers who have not taught during the pandemic or have

limited experience with remote or hybrid teaching modalities; and teachers who are unwilling to participate in the study or provide detailed information about their experiences with technology integration were excluded in the study.

2.5. *Data Collection*—Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City; and the ethical clearance certificate from RMC-Research Ethics Committee (RMC-REC). The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City; and the ethical clearance certificate from RMC-Research Ethics Committee (RMC-REC) were attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected public schools in Laak South District in Davao de Oro. Gathering of Data. The researcher conducted in-depth interviews with fatherless children and their respective teachers and mothers to gather rich and detailed information about their experiences integrating technology in the classroom. These interviews were structured to explore various aspects of the teachers' experiences, including their interactions with colleagues and peers, their engagement in teaching, and any challenges or barriers they encountered. The interviews were conducted in a private and comfortable setting, such as the teachers' homes or schools, to ensure confidentiality and encourage open communication. The researcher used open-ended questions and prompts to elicit detailed responses from the teachers, allowing them to share their thoughts, feelings, and experiences in their own words.

During the interviews, the researcher took detailed notes and recorded audio or video with the participants' consent. This allowed for a comprehensive record of the interviews, capturing the nuances of the teachers' responses and providing rich data for analysis. Collation and Analysis of Data. After conducting the in-depth interview and focus group discussions with teachers, the researcher compiled the audio or video recordings, along with detailed notes taken during the interviews, to create a comprehensive dataset. Each interview was labeled and organized according to participant pseudonyms to maintain confidentiality. The researcher transcribed the interview recordings verbatim and reviewed the transcripts to identify key themes, patterns, and insights related to the teachers' technology integration knowledge. This involved using qualitative analysis techniques such as thematic coding, where recurring themes and concepts were systematically identified and categorized. All datasets from in-depth interviews and focus group discussion from participants were integrated into a single dataset for analysis. This allowed for a comprehensive and holistic examination of the teachers' experiences, incorporating multiple perspectives and sources of information. The researcher conducted a cross-sectional analysis of the integrated dataset, examining the convergence and divergence of themes across different data sources. This involved synthesizing findings from interviews to develop a nuanced understanding of the factors influencing the teachers' experiences.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—

Thematic analysis of in-depth interviews involved identifying patterns, themes, and recurring concepts within the transcribed interview data. The researcher familiarized themselves with the interview transcripts by reading through them multiple times to gain a comprehensive understanding of the data. The researcher systematically coded the transcripts, assigning descriptive labels to segments of text that captured key ideas, concepts, or patterns related to the technology integration knowledge of teachers. Codes were grouped into higher-order themes based on their relevance and similarity. Themes were refined through iterative analysis, with the researcher constantly comparing and contrasting codes to identify overarching patterns and concepts. The researcher reviewed the identified themes, examining their coherence, relevance, and significance in relation to the research questions. Themes were interpreted in light of the study's objectives and theoretical frameworks.

3. Results and Discussion

The data analysis presented in this chapter is the outcome of the study. In addition, discussions are provided to provide a full explanation of the themes that were generated in response to the objectives established for this study.

3.1. Lived Experiences of Teachers as Regard to Technology Integration Knowledge Within COVID-19 Crisis Set-Up—The lived experiences of teachers as regard to technology integration knowledge within COVID-19 crisis set-up are presented in Figure 3. The figure showed a Adoption on Online Teaching with three subthemes namely: Technological proficiency and skills development; pedagogical innovations and experimentation; and lesson planning and curriculum adaptation.

3.1.1. Adoption on Online Teaching—The essential theme generated as regard to experiences of teachers is adoption on online teaching. This indicates that amidst the pandemic, online teaching platforms and digital tools played a pivotal role in education. They became indispensable tools for delivering instruction, accessing educational content, and facilitating communication channels between teachers and students. Teachers who possessed advanced skills in integrating technology into their teaching practices were more adept at utilizing these resources to enhance the learning experiences of their students.

3.1.2. Technological proficiency and skills development—Teachers' experiences in developing their technological proficiency and skills to effectively use digital tools and platforms for remote instruction are integral to enhancing teaching-learning processes, empowering educators to deliver engaging, inclusive, and impactful learning experiences that prepare students for success in the digital age.

3.1.3. Pedagogical Innovations and Experimentation—During the pandemic, when traditional classroom settings were disrupted and remote learning became the norm, teachers relied heavily on technology to deliver instruction. In this landscape, pedagogical innovations played a crucial role in helping educators adapt their teaching methods to the online environ-

Fig. 3. Lived Experiences of the Participants Regard to as regard to Technology Integration Skills

ment. Experimenting with new teaching strategies, tools, and technologies became essential for maintaining student engagement, promoting active learning, and ensuring the continuity of education.

3.1.4. Lesson Planning and Curriculum Adaptation—This subtheme examines how teachers have adapted their lesson planning and curriculum development processes to incorporate technology effectively into remote instruction, ensuring alignment with learning objectives and standards.

3.2. Coping Mechanism of Teachers with the Challenges in Relation to Technology Integration within COVID-19 Crisis Set-Up—The coping mechanism of the participants on the challenges in relation to technology integration skills within COVID-19 Crisis Set-Up. Reflected on Figure 4 is the theme Professional Development for Remote Learning with three subthemes namely: Online workshops and training; individualized professional development plans; and peer learning communities.

3.2.1. Professional Development for Remote Learning—During the pandemic, when traditional classroom settings were disrupted, teachers had to swiftly adapt to online instruction. Professional development initiatives focused on remote learning aimed to support educators in mastering digital tools, understanding online pedagogies, and designing engaging virtual lessons. This theme underscores the crucial role of continuous learning and upskilling among teachers to ensure the delivery of quality education despite the constraints imposed by remote learning environments.

3.2.2. Online workshops and training—Online workshops and training for teachers during the pandemic represent a crucial avenue for professional development and skill enhancement in the realm of technology integration. These sessions offer educators valuable opportu-

Fig. 4. Participants’ Coping Mechanism with Regards to the Integrating Technology In the Classroom Within COVID-19 Crisis Set-Up

nities to upgrade their proficiency in using digital tools and platforms for teaching purposes. By actively participating in such workshops, teachers can gain insights into effective strategies for technology integration in the online classroom, ultimately boosting their confidence in navigating the digital landscape of education.

3.2.3. Individualized Professional Development Plans—With the sudden shift to online learning, educators required specialized support to navigate the digital landscape effectively. These individualized plans allowed teachers to focus on areas where they required further training or development, ensuring that their professional growth aligned closely with the demands of remote instruction. This theme highlights the importance of personalized learning pathways for educators to thrive in the rapidly evolving educational landscape brought about by the pandemic

3.2.4. Peer Learning Communities—During the pandemic, teachers faced numerous challenges in adapting to remote and hybrid teaching environments, particularly in integrating technology effectively into their instructional practices. Peer learning communities emerged as invaluable support systems for educators grappling with these challenges.

3.3. Skills Develop in Integrating Technology in the Classroom—The skills, develop among the participants is presented on the Figure 5 below. The figure shows that there are three themes namely; Digital literacy enhancement; curriculum integration; and tech tools exploration.

3.3.1. Digital Literacy Enhancement—Improved digital literacy empowers educators to access a wealth of online resources such as educational websites, digital libraries, and interactive learning platforms. This access expands the range of teaching materials available, enriching the teaching-learning process.

3.3.2. Curriculum Integration—Curriculum integration with technology allows educators to adapt their instructional materials and

Fig. 5. Skills Develop in Integrating Technology in the Classroom

methods to different learning environments, including remote, hybrid, or in-person settings. By seamlessly blending technology into the curriculum, teachers can ensure continuity in learning regardless of the mode of instruction.

3.3.3. Tech Tools Exploration—Tech tools exploration enhances the integration of technology in the classroom by empowering educators to discover and leverage digital resources that support student learning and engagement. It promotes professional growth, fosters collaboration, and cultivates a culture of innovation, ultimately enriching the teaching and learning experience for both educators and students.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This part of the paper presents the implications and future directions of the study. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters and the implications is in accordance with research questions presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary purpose of the study was to explore the lived experiences of the teachers in public elementary schools in Laak South District, Davao de Oro as regards to the technology integration knowledge in the classroom within COVID-19 crisis set-up using qualitative approach, specifically, the phenomenological design wherein a semi-structured interview guide was administered through in-depth interview (IDI) and focus group discussion (FGD). The researcher selected the 17 public elementary school teachers from Laak South District, Davao de Oro as the participants through purposive sampling method. The researcher made use of semi-structured interview guide to gather data on the lived experiences of the teachers in elementary schools as regards to the technology integration knowledge in the classroom within COVID-19 crisis set-up. Based on the results the summary of the findings were the following: Adaptation to online teaching was the emerging theme on the lived experiences of the teachers as regard to the technology integration knowledge of teachers in public elementary schools. This was supported with three subthemes namely: technolog-

ical proficiency and skills development; pedagogical innovations and experimentation; and lesson planning and curriculum adaptation. This indicates that amidst the pandemic, online teaching platforms and digital tools played a pivotal role in education. They became indispensable tools for delivering instruction, accessing educational content, and facilitating communication channels between teachers and students. Professional development for remote learning was the theme emerged on the participants' coping mechanism with regards to the challenges in relation to technology integration within COVID-19 set-up. The subthemes were as follows: online workshops and training; individualized professional development plans; and peer learning communities. This theme underscores the crucial role of continuous learning and upskilling among teachers to ensure the delivery of qual-

4.2. Implications—As regard to the lived experiences of the participants on the technology integration in the classroom, teachers require continuous support and professional development opportunities to bolster their technological proficiency and skills. This can be achieved through various means such as workshops, training sessions, or online courses tailored to familiarize educators with a plethora of digital tools, platforms, and resources essential for online teaching. By providing ongoing support and relevant professional development, educators can stay abreast of the latest technological advancements, refine their digital competencies, and effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. This, in turn, enables teachers to create engaging and interactive learning experiences for their students, fostering a conducive environment for effective online education. Additionally, teachers should be encouraged to explore innovative pedagogical approaches and experiment with new teaching methods tailored to the online learning envi-

ity education despite the constraints imposed by remote learning environments. The thematic analysis indicated the there are three themes generated on the skills develop in integrating technology in the classroom. This included: digital literacy enhancement; curriculum integration; and tech tools exploration. Improved digital literacy empowers educators to access a wealth of online resources such as educational websites, digital libraries, and interactive learning platforms. Also, curriculum integration with technology allows educators to adapt their instructional materials and methods to different learning environments, including remote, hybrid, or in-person settings. Lastly, Tech tools exploration enhances the integration of technology in the classroom by empowering educators to discover and leverage digital resources that support student learning and engagement.

ronment. This may entail integrating interactive multimedia elements, gamified activities, virtual simulations, and other engaging instructional strategies into their online lessons. By embracing innovation and experimentation, educators can create dynamic and interactive learning experiences that captivate students' interest and enhance their engagement in online learning. Additionally, by adapting teaching methods to suit the digital landscape, teachers can effectively address diverse learning needs and preferences, ultimately fostering a more enriching and inclusive online learning environment. Moreover, teachers must adapt their lesson planning and curriculum design strategies to effectively deliver instruction in an online format. This adaptation may require them to redesign existing lesson plans, select suitable digital resources, and integrate technology-enhanced activities that align with learning objectives and student needs. By embracing technology in lesson planning, educators can create more interactive and engaging learning experiences that

cater to diverse learning styles and preferences. Additionally, by incorporating digital tools and resources, teachers can provide students with opportunities for active learning, collaboration, and creativity, thus maximizing the effectiveness of online instruction. As to the coping mechanism of teachers, educational institutions should prioritize providing comprehensive training and support programs focused on technology integration for remote learning. Workshops, seminars, and online courses can be organized to help teachers develop the necessary skills and competencies for effective remote teaching. By offering such training opportunities, institutions can empower teachers to navigate the challenges of remote instruction with confidence and competence. Additionally, ongoing support mechanisms, such as peer mentoring and coaching, can be established to provide teachers with guidance and assistance as they adapt to new technologies and teaching methods. By investing in the professional development of teachers, educational institutions can ensure that they are better equipped to cope with the demands of remote learning and deliver high-quality instruction to their students. As regard to the skills developed in integrating technology in the classroom, digital literacy enhancement should be integrated into ongoing professional development initiatives. Teachers should have access to workshops, courses, and resources that support the development of digital literacy skills relevant to their teaching practices. By incorporating digital literacy training into professional development programs, educational institutions can ensure that teachers are equipped with the knowledge and skills needed to effectively integrate technology into their teaching. This can include training on how to use digital tools for

lesson planning, content creation, and student assessment, as well as guidance on how to critically evaluate online resources and promote digital citizenship among students. More so, promoting interdisciplinary approaches to curriculum integration can enrich student learning experiences. Teachers can collaborate across subject areas to design integrated units of study that leverage technology to explore complex topics and real-world problems. By integrating multiple disciplines, such as science, mathematics, language arts, and social studies, teachers can provide students with a holistic understanding of a topic and help them make connections between different areas of knowledge. Technology can enhance interdisciplinary learning by providing access to diverse resources, facilitating communication and collaboration among students, and enabling the creation of multimedia projects that showcase their understanding. Adding more, establishing professional learning communities focused on tech tools exploration can support teachers in discovering and sharing innovative educational technologies. These communities can provide opportunities for collaboration, experimentation, and peer learning around the effective use of tech tools. By coming together to explore new tools, teachers can exchange ideas, share best practices, and troubleshoot challenges they encounter. This collaborative approach can help teachers stay abreast of emerging technologies and pedagogical practices, ensuring that they remain at the forefront of educational innovation. Additionally, professional learning communities can provide a sense of camaraderie and support, empowering teachers to take risks and experiment with new tools in their classrooms.

4.3. *Future Directions*—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant

people whom this research was intended for. Thus, the researcher recommends the following: The Department of Education should prior-

itize investments in infrastructure and resources to support teachers' technological proficiency. This includes ensuring access to reliable internet connectivity, providing adequate digital devices, and offering technical support to address technology-related challenges. In many remote areas, limited internet connectivity and insufficient digital devices pose significant barriers to effective technology integration in education. By investing in infrastructure such as broadband internet access and digital devices like tablets or laptops, the Department of Education can help bridge the digital divide and ensure that all teachers have the tools they need to effectively leverage technology in their teaching practices. School leaders should create a supportive environment that encourages risk-taking and experimentation among teachers. By fostering a culture of innovation and providing autonomy in curriculum design and instructional delivery, school leaders can empower teachers to explore creative approaches to online teaching. One key aspect of creating a supportive environment is providing teachers with autonomy in curriculum design and instructional delivery. School leaders can empower teachers to take ownership of their teaching by allowing them the flexibility to design lessons that meet the needs and interests of their students. This may involve encouraging teachers to experiment with different teaching methods, incorporate new technologies, and explore innovative pedagogical approaches. Training sessions should focus not only on technical skills but also on effective instructional strategies for engaging students, promoting collaboration, and fostering deeper learning experiences. Teachers can learn how to use interactive multimedia resources to create engaging presentations that capture students' interest and encourage active participation. They can also explore digital collaboration platforms that facilitate group work and collaborative projects, allowing students to work together on tasks and share ideas in real-time.

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